

RELATIONSHIP OF PEDAGOGY WITH OTHER SCIENCES AND SYSTEM OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

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ANNOTATION: This article describes the relationship of pedagogy with other disciplines and the system of pedagogic sciences.

KEYWORDS: Didactics, Didaskal, teaching, imparting knowledge.

Teachers and students who are citizens of every country should know the history of their motherland and be patriotic. It is impossible to be a teacher without knowing the history of education and the history of pedagogy.

The teacher has a systematic influence on the students in order to give them knowledge, make them knowledgeable, and educate them. It is based on psychological and social factors. That is, in order to find out the effect of the influence, he determines the plan of influence based on knowing how the student's intuition, perception, imagination, attention and thinking, thinking process is going. In particular, it is necessary for a teacher to have deep knowledge of the psychology of youth. A teacher who knows this well approaches the child taking into account the age and individual characteristics of each child and can effectively influence him. In a certain sense, psychological sciences that serve teachers can also be included in the system of pedagogic sciences. Philosophy serves as a methodological basis for the science of pedagogy. Philosophy equips pedagogy with scientific methods and becomes a source for development of objective laws and regulations of education and upbringing. The science of ethics and aesthetics provides information on the educational theory section of pedagogy. This science is related to the science of pedagogy in terms of defining and determining the standards of the student's behavior and manners, as well as explaining beauty in the true sense of the word, directly stimulating the attractive and elegant aspects of life in the student's mind. Ways of teaching subjects are related to didactics, because the method of teaching any subject serves to master the content and system of this subject by students. Therefore, the science of pedagogy has a strong relationship with such disciplines as children's anatomy, physiology, children's hygiene and pediatrics, these sciences are closely related to each other.

Pedagogical branches of theoretical and practical aspects of teaching and educating students in various fields illuminates.

Modern pedagogy should solve the important issues of raising people working in the spheres of social life to be educated, perfect people who can withstand competition in the conditions of the market economy, are highly conscious, can think independently, and become an example to others with their behavior. If we can form healthy beliefs and a high worldview in our youth from childhood, they will grow up to be spiritually rich, independent-minded and

noble individuals. Ideological worldview and national ideas are formed on the basis of such beliefs. National independence

The role of our national customs and traditions, families and neighborhoods, especially educational institutions, is very important in inculcating the idea into the minds and hearts of young people, and this also sets great tasks for the science of pedagogy. What methods, tools and ways to manage the educational process

Pedagogy determines the necessity.

Another important concept of pedagogy is the word "Didactics". In ancient Greece, a person who taught a slave's child at school was called "Didaskal". "Didactic" is derived from the Greek word "didaktikos" and means "to teach", "to impart knowledge".

Now, the scope and content of these concepts has become much richer and expanded, and it includes not only the activity of the teacher, but also the activity of the student. The main categories of pedagogy are education, training, information, development, pedagogical activity, pedagogical process, knowledge, consists of educational methods, principles, etc. them we call pedagogical concepts.

Education is the systematic influence of the educator on the mentality of the students in order to instill the desired qualities into their minds. Due to the fact that the term "education" is evaluated as a comprehensive concept in world pedagogy, there are different theories about its essence. Understanding education as the process of influencing children by adults (teachers, coaches and parents) is the most common tendency. In this place, the ideals, goals that adults consider correct, it is expected to influence in accordance with tasks, norms and requirements, of course.

This understanding of education is closer to the truth, but it has a completely subjective nature and reflects only a certain part of this process. In this definition of education, the child is considered only as an object directed to the influence of adults. If pedagogy also refers to the training of initiative and independent individuals, the role of an active subject in the pedagogical process is given to the student.

References:

- 1.Голдаев, С. В., & Хушвактов, А. А. (2014). Анализ вариантов осушения влажного воздуха с помощью силикагеля при консервации агрегатов пароводяного тракта тепловой электрической станции. Известия Томского политехнического университета. Инжиниринг георесурсов, 325(2), 120-126.
- 2.Khalmuradov, R., Khudoynazarov, K., & Isabekov, K. (2023). Experimental study of vibrations of cross-rod spatial structures. In E3S Web of Conferences (Vol. 365, p. 02006). EDP Sciences.
- 3.Melikulov, N., & Khushvaktov, U. Stability of Long Plates with Non-Symmetric Reinforcement of the Edges with Thin-Walled Rods. MIDDLE EUROPEAN SCIENTIFIC BULLETIN [Middle European Scientific Bulletin, VOLUME 19 Dec 2021.